

SHORT NOTES

Substituted 3-Aminobenzo/f/quinolines

A. K. Chatterjee

Chatterjee (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1960, **25**, 1050) reported preparation of a number of derivatives of 1-amino-3-methylbenzo/f/quinoline for trials against *E. histolytica*. The present communication deals with the preparation of some derivatives of 3-amino-1-methylbenzo/f_iquinoline as potential amoebicides.

The compounds were prepared by the condensation of 3-chloro-1-methylbenzo/f/-quinoline with the appropriate amine in boiling amyl alcohol and characterised as salicylates.

The condensation of ethyl acetoacetate with 2-naphthylamine and subsequent cyclisation of the product in concentrated hydrochloric acid according to Albert *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 1284) gave 3-hydroxy-1-methylbenzo/f/quinoline, which was converted into the 3-chloro derivative by treatment with phosphorus oxychloride.

General Method of Preparation

3-Chloro-1-methylbenzo/f/quinoline (0.01M) was dissolved in amylⁿ alcohol (30 c.c.) by heating and a slight excess of the appropriate amine added. The mixture was boiled under reflux for 20 hours.

The hydrochloride of the base separated on cooling. It was filtered, washed with ether, and dissolved in boiling dilute acetic acid. The solution was made alkaline with aqueous NaOH when the base separated as a sticky solid, which quickly solidified. This was filtered, washed with water, dried, and dissolved in hot benzene. The small amount of insoluble matter was removed by filtration and the filtrate treated with a solution of salicylic acid in ether. In a few hours, the salicylate of the base separated which, after filtration and washing with ether, was purified by crystallising thrice from benzene. The compounds are listed in Table J.

TABLE I

Compound.	Formula.	M.P.	%Carbon.		%Hydrogen.	
			Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
3- <i>p</i> -Chloroanilino-MQ	$C_{20}H_{13}N_2Cl.C_7H_6O_3$	213°	71.26	70.97	4.79	4.60
3- <i>m</i> -Chloroanilino-MQ	$C_{20}H_{13}N_2Cl.C_7H_6O_3$	195°	71.10	70.97	4.65	4.60
3- <i>p</i> -Bromoanilino-MQ	$C_{20}H_{13}N_2Br.C_7H_6O_3$	218°	64.97	64.67	4.33	4.19
3- <i>m</i> -Bromoanilino-MQ	$C_{20}H_{13}N_2Br.C_7H_6O_3$	198°	64.71	64.67	4.53	4.19
3- <i>m</i> -Iodoanilino-MQ	$C_{20}H_{13}N_2I.C_7H_6O_3$	196°	58.85	59.11	3.76	3.83
3-Anilino-MQ	$C_{20}H_{16}N_2.C_7H_6O_3$	220°	77.00	76.78	5.42	5.21
3- <i>p</i> -Toluidino-MQ	$C_{21}H_{18}N_2.C_7H_6O_3$	220°	77.06	77.06	5.27	5.50
3- <i>m</i> -Toluidino-MQ	$C_{21}H_{18}N_2.C_7H_6O_3$	192°	77.43	77.06	5.74	5.50
3- <i>p</i> -Anisidino-MQ	$C_{21}H_{18}N_2O.C_7H_6O_3$	199.5°	73.99	74.34	5.47	5.31

N.B. MQ stands for 1-methylbenzo[*h*]quinoline salicylate. $C_7H_6O_3$ = salicylic acid.

DEPARTMENT OF PREVENTIVE MEDICINE,
ARMED FORCES MEDICAL COLLEGE,
POONA-1.

Received August 12, 1961.